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道德命題是否能作為感知內容呢？

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摘要

內容型道德感知主義者（Contentful Moral Perceptualists）： Audi (2013), Lord (2018), McNaughton (1988), McBrayer (2010a, 2010b), Cowan (2014, 2015), Werner (2016, 2018) 宣稱道德命題(moral proposition)可以作為道德主體的感知內容(content of perception)。然而，在筆者原創的詮釋下，晚近反駁道德感知主義的學者，如： Faraci (2015), Väyrynen (2018), Chudnoff (2015)，則隱約透露出以下想法：「與其宣稱道德命題是感知內容，不如宣稱道德命題是認知信念內容(content of cognition)」更為合理」。Faraci、Väyrynen、Chudnoff 都認為「內容型道德感知主義者所謂的道德感知」背後其實是受到宰制型的道德原則（dominative moral principles）所主導的，是一種從原則所推論產生的心理狀態；也因此，上述反駁者認為「內容型道德感知主義者所謂的〔道德感知〕」缺乏貨真價實的感知經驗所具有的「非推論的」(non-inferential)特徵，並不是真正的感知。本文將評估：「內容型的道德感知模型」是否有辦法回應上述反駁者所提出的挑戰呢？筆者將為肯定的答案提供初步的辯護。

關鍵詞：道德感知、現象對比方法、感知內容、現象經驗、感知的非推論特徵

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